

PLACEMENT OF GRADUATES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE LABOR MARKET

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Abstract. *The article reveals the specific features of the labor market for graduates of higher education institutions as a special segment of the general labor market, identifies the subjects and institutions of this segment of the labor market, defines the laws of their interaction, develops a model of the social labor market, assesses the current state of the labor market for graduates of cooperation, higher education institutions, indicates the main problem areas that cause tension in this segment of the labor market; the complex reveals the analytical possibilities of the main theoretical models and concepts determining the activity of the labor market for university graduates, including: the model of individual labor supply, the model of investments in human capital, the model of educational signals, theory incompleteness and asymmetry of information on the labor market, the theory of social capital, the concept of human development, the concept of decent work, etc., factors determining the demand of employers for young professionals in the context of professional changes, the qualification structure of expanding employment and higher education opportunities was defined and systematized.*

Based on original empirical data, a classification of strategies, methods and tools used by employers when entering the labor market was carried out, and the needs of companies for the functions and services of labor exchange institutions for university graduates were identified.

Keywords: *labor market segment, econometric calculation, empirical data, intra-company adaptation, labor orientation and motivation.*

Introduction: According to surveys conducted among employers, university graduates do not always meet their requirements in terms of their level of preparation and acquired qualifications. At the same time, the graduates themselves are dissatisfied with the offered work, salary and working conditions, and often refuse to get a job in their specialty. Together, this leads to the low efficiency of the use of the labor of young professionals, which allows us to raise the issue of "overproduction" of highly educated specialists and the unsatisfactory quality of their training. The republic's higher educational institutions graduate about 1,150,000 specialists every year. The labor market of graduates of Uzbekistan's higher educational institutions was formed during the next 12-15 years under the influence of the following main factors. There is an objectively determined contradiction between the possibilities of training a specialist at the university and the need for his knowledge and skills in the labor market - the time interval between the beginning of the educational process and the entry of the graduate into the labor market is quantitatively determined [1-4]. The inertia of the vocational education system exacerbates this gap between education and work, and the difficulty of placing graduates of higher education institutions in the context of a radical change in the professional and sectoral structure of employment increases dramatically. The collapse of the compulsory state distribution system, which existed during the Soviet era and covered almost all graduates of higher education institutions, caused university graduates to face the problem of finding work independently, most of them for this were not ready. A gap has emerged between universities and employers, which in

some cases has yet to be filled. Since the early 2000s, significant changes have taken place in the vector of higher education development, the dynamics of changes aimed at increasing the level of compliance with the modern requirements of the innovative economy and the labor market have increased. In our country, there was a trend of transition to a knowledge-based economy associated with the development of new technologies, changes in the structure of population employment, globalization of economic relations and increased competition. The demand for higher education has increased dramatically in recent years, while the need for skilled workers in the labor market remains unmet. In the composition of labor resources, imbalances have appeared due to the inefficient behavior of households in investing in education, the reason for which is the asymmetry of information: universities, in the context of an absolute reduction in the number of young people is sharply increasing the attraction of applicants, while objective information on the prospects of labor demand is not sufficiently available for households.

Main Part: Historical experience shows that even with a stable economic situation and the relative availability of labor market information, a large proportion of graduates are not ready to make the transition from education to work. The problems of finding and choosing the first job for a university graduate are becoming more acute in the conditions of high socio-economic uncertainty and risks that arise in times of economic recession and crises.

Socio-economic instability and political tension are putting great pressure on the youth as a demographic group that is considered both socially vulnerable and socially dangerous.

The lack of demand for graduates of higher education institutions, dissatisfaction with their financial situation and position in society can cause their deviant behavior and lead to major socio-political explosions, as happened in the recent history of a number of countries. In such conditions, effective social partnership, including active regulatory activity of the state, is of particular importance [5-6].

The need to make scientifically based and effective management decisions in the field of ensuring the work and employment of graduates of higher educational institutions in our country is emphasized by the segmentation of regional, branch and professional qualification labor markets, the multinational component of the workforce, and the intensification of migration processes is wanted lack of demand for specialists and lack of suitable conditions for their work and brain drain related to others.

Thus, both the objective limitation of the ability of higher education institutions to quickly respond to dynamic changes in the labor market and the aggravation of the problem of providing employment to graduates of higher education institutions in the current socio-economic situation in the country were caused by changes employment structure and limited interaction between employers and universities.

A comprehensive approach to the problem of studying the position and behavior of university graduates in the labor market includes consideration of a set of directions that make it up, including: the economic theory of labor, the concept of human development, the concept of decent work; development patterns of the labor market, its segmentation, interaction with the market of educational services, characteristics of youth employment as a separate socio-demographic group, the impact of higher education on the position of workers in the labor market, as well as employment of graduates of higher education institutions, a number of issues related to improving methods and technologies and improving the activities of institutions in this segment of the labor market.

The modern labor market is considered in the work as a complex socio-economic phenomenon with a complex component, and the activity of the labor market is considered as an interaction of its subjects: workers, employers and the state in the most effective use of labor resources in the process of implementing tasks of socio-economic development of the society. A classic tool for analyzing the labor market - its segmentation made it possible to better understand the reasons for the behavior of its subjects, more accurately predict the trends of changes, develop targeted policies in the field of labor relations and effective measures of effective regulation.

The science recognized the duality of the labor market, that is, the market is divided into primary and secondary according to the educational potential and the quality of jobs. Segmentation refers to the global, country, regional, local territorial distribution of the labor market;

identification of industry and professional qualification labor markets;

specifications of regulated and unregulated labor markets, etc.

The author's determination of the labor market of university graduates as a unique segment of the total labor market is based on the following evidence:

1) characteristics of university graduates as a group of workers with a set of objective and subjective unique characteristics - the presence having a higher education, the demand for highly qualified and highly paid jobs, the absence or lack of work experience, underdeveloped job search skills and insufficient self-esteem;

2) the specificity of the demand for university graduates by employers, which is the emphasis of their requirements for knowledge (high quality, relevance, ability to receive and process information), personal qualities (enthusiasm, high mobility, openness) it consists of priorities new knowledge and ideas), as well as focusing on the brand of the university as an indicator of the quality of its graduates;

3) the presence of relevant institutions regulating this segment of the labor market, including the legal framework defining the labor relations of its subjects, as well as organizations and services that form the infrastructure of this market. A characteristic feature of the labor market for university graduates is the complexity of its subjects and the uncertainty of the causal relationships of its components. Thus, on the labor supply side, the main topic is a university graduate, but the decision about entering the labor market, choosing a work mode, and the requirements for the quality of work, as a rule, is not taken by the individual, but by the household, as well as deciding on the choice of a university, personnel training, specialization, etc. The priorities of the household are determined by its objective economic interest, financial situation, goals and values, national characteristics, established traditions, etc. An entity in this segment of the labor market is also a higher education institution with its own economic interests. The university plays a dual role in the labor exchange: firstly, as a labor supply side, the university is responsible for the quality of knowledge and skills, preparing graduates for independent work, organizing internships and internships, and is interested in effective labor activity. employment of graduates. Second, the university acts as a party to the demand for labor force, as it needs to replenish and renew its scientific and pedagogical staff and becomes a place of employment for some graduates [7-8].

Subjects of demand for work of graduates of higher educational institutions are the real sector of the economy, business, research structures (institutes, centers), public service and universities. A distinctive feature of the modern Russian labor market is the presence of a significant difference in the solvency of various entities acting on the side of labor demand. Taking

into account the diversity of the subjects of this segment of the labor market makes it possible to draw up directions for regulating its development. The complexity and diversity of the interests of the subjects of the labor market of university graduates explains the contradictions between the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the graduates and the need for labor of the labor market, which can cause acute socio-political conflicts. As social partners, directions for the development and improvement of mutual cooperation between the subjects of the labor market of university graduates were determined, which allows to reduce imbalances in the labor market and increase the efficiency of the use of labor resources.

2. Analytical capabilities of the main theoretical models and concepts determining the activity of the university graduates' labor exchange. Studying the university graduates' labor exchange, determining the factors determining the behavior of its subjects, requires the unification and systematization of the methodology the foundations of different scientific schools and concepts. This approach opens up new opportunities for analyzing, evaluating, forecasting and managing the behavior of subjects in this segment of the labor market.

The work focuses on such methodological concepts as the economic theory of labor, the theory of human capital, the theory of social capital, the concept of human development, the concept of decent work, including relevant models and indicator systems.

To analyze the main models of the behavior of university graduates and employers in the labor market, the main models and rules of the economic theory of labor were used: simple and extended models of labor supply and demand, spider web model of demand for specialist labor, the theory of information asymmetry in the labor market, the theory of job search, etc.

It is shown that the economic importance of education for the successful employment of a university graduate is revealed with the help of theories of human capital and educational signals.

According to human capital theory, a higher level of education brings additional income to an employee. Currently, a broader interpretation of human capital has become widespread: knowledge, skills, competencies and properties of individuals that contribute to the creation of personal, social and economic well-being. Thus, human capital includes any properties of individuals, for example, the natural level of abilities. Data from the International Adult Literacy Survey have shown that human capital components such as gender, age, education, literacy, experience, parental education and knowledge of the language of the country of residence explain 20-50% of the differences in earnings at the labor exchange. The use of econometric analysis allows us to assess the significance (strength and direction) of the influence of individual characteristics (gender, age, education, abilities, education of parents, siblings, work experience, presence of a spouse, children, etc.) on the employee's earnings.

The emergence of this analysis technique, along with the creation of appropriate databases, allows for a comprehensive factor analysis of the employee's economic situation.

Systematization of domestic and foreign statistical and empirical data indicating that the quality of the education received has a significant impact on a worker's income. This factor is complex and depends both on the quality of the educational services provided and on the success of their perception on the part of the student [9-10].

According to the theory of educational signals, it is assumed that obtaining a higher education requires special effort and special abilities, and for people who are not inclined to mental activity, the costs of obtaining higher education will be unacceptably high. Then the presence of a

diploma of higher education becomes a kind of guarantee of a person's abilities for intellectual work and serves as a signal to the employer.

The influence of education on an individual as an employee from the point of view of the theory of educational signals can be calculated through the return on the level of education. This assessment is especially important for graduates entering the labor market for the first time, because the employer, when assessing the attractiveness of an employee with no experience, often relies not on the number of years of study completed, but on the level of the diploma received. Statistics showing the jump in income of workers as they move to the next level of education: the difference in income between those who leave a university after studying there for one or three years is significantly less than for either of these groups compared to certified graduates. The state of the labor market of university graduates conducted on the basis of these concepts showed that modern employers pay attention not only to the level of education, but also to which educational institution they studied, which form of education, which form of education and whether education meets established standards. The student's success in understanding the knowledge given at the university is evaluated by the employer based on the grades in the diploma, and the honors diploma is usually taken as an indicator of the seriousness, responsibility and discipline of the future employee.

The theory of human capital is not without its advantages, which should be taken into account when constructing a research hypothesis and developing conclusions based on it. Firstly, the problem of the ability to pay for the work of an educated worker is completely ignored. Secondly, received only in most cases and not included, received in a non-traditional form: access to benefits, social benefits and compensation, income from self-employment, etc., which technologically cannot be taken into account and included in comparison. Thirdly, only quantitative, and not qualitative, parameters of the benefits received and costs incurred are taken into account [11-12]. The influence of such factors as the status of the workplace, the content of the work performed, access to resources, to power, to management, opportunities for creative self-realization, working hours, etc is not taken into account. Fourth, the limited information base still makes it impossible to assess changes in income throughout the entire life cycle: as a rule, one-time sections are considered, rather than evolutionary changes occurring with individuals under different economic conditions.

Thus, a comprehensive analysis involving non-financial components and socially oriented theory is necessary to have a reliable picture of the value of the labor market of university graduates.

With all the importance of education, especially higher education, parameters such as profession, specialty, where the certified specialist is, geographically and in which company he intends to apply his knowledge in practice are of great importance.

The experience gained by the employee at the workplace is considered as a kind of human capital in scientific research. In theory, the greater the return on practical experience, the more profitable it is to work rather than study, the less attractive it is to study as a form of adjustment in the labor market, and the more profitable it is to serve longer labor relations at one workplace.

In modern economics, human capital theory, and educational signaling theory in general, very successfully explains the earnings and employment advantages of higher education, but does not explain the causes of problems among university graduates during the transition from study to work and making it difficult to earn a high income.

Conclusion: The importance of higher education for a person is not limited only to the possibility of earning money. In this regard, it becomes relevant to consider education as a factor in the formation of social capital, since higher education is widely recognized in research as a social elevator, that is, the most effective opportunity to overcome social and caste barriers there is a view climbing the social ladder. The demand for education as a social good is based not only on employment opportunities, but also on the fact that the fate of the whole person, his worldview, goals and values, lifestyle and quality are largely determined by his society, that is, the social environment in which it exists. In this sense, the desire of parents to provide higher education to their children comes from the desire to provide comfortable and promising conditions for their future life. Not only theoretical knowledge and practical skills, but also the experience of teamwork and communication in a student environment, as well as the acquaintances, contacts, connections established during studies will further help the graduate in building a career. It is known that university graduates join groups and associations, which help support their participants in the labor market as one of their goals. Thus, at present, the social component of higher education is a factor of ensuring effective employment. Thus, the modern economic theory of labor has a fundamental basis for analyzing the impact of higher education on the worker's income, and statistical and econometric analysis tools together with the indicators reflected in the concepts of social orientation make it possible to make a reliable assessment. This affects the position of university graduates in the labor market.

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